

WEAR MODELS FOR MULTIPHASE MATERIALS AND SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS IN POLYMERIC HYBRID COMPOSITES

K. Friedrich

Institute for Composite Materials Ltd.
6750 Kaiserslautern, Germany

ABSTRACT

This paper presents some of the existing approaches for mathematically describing the friction and wear behaviour of multi-component systems. The relationship between the size of the reinforcing phase and the asperity size plays an important role in friction and wear phenomena.

The abrasive wear of particle-reinforced polymer composites can be described by a simple additive equation based on a series model. If these composites are, however, subjected to sliding wear against smooth steel counterparts, the simple rule of mixtures description does not apply anymore, due to a wider complexity of the wear mechanisms.

From investigations on the unlubricated friction and wear of the unidirectionally oriented fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) slid against carbon steel, the following results were obtained: 1) Carbon-FRP possess lower specific wear rates and friction coefficients than glass-FRP. 2) A model was proposed that the wear of FRP proceeds by the wear-thinning of the fiber with subsequent breakdown of the fiber and by peeling-off of the fiber from the matrix.

Further works regarding the tribological behaviour of hybrid composites have lead to the following conclusions: 1) Using the best wear results achieved with monolithic fiber composites, i.e. with carbon fibers oriented in-plane and parallel to the sliding direction, or with aramid fibers in normal orientation, would lead to a model composite with a 3-D-hybrid structure, which is supposed to possess optimum wear resistance. 2) Approching this model by producing 2-D-hybrid composites shows synergistic effects between different fiber materials and directions chosen.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites with continuous-fiber reinforcement of high volume fraction and perfect alignment are known to possess very high values to specific strength and stiffness. Little has yet been published, however, on secondary properties, as, for instance, the composite friction and wear behaviour.

The objectives of this paper were (a) to summarize some of existing models for describing the wear behaviour of multiphase materials in general, (b) to especially focus at those results which have been found for fiber reinforced composites under the special condition that more than one type of reinforcing component was used in a certain polymeric matrix, (c) to report about recent works for developing hybrid composites with high wear resistance, and (d) to establish a model which describes the positive or negative synergistic wear effects resulting from hybridization of different fiber materials in one particular composite system.

2. RULE OF MIXTURES APPROACHES TO WEAR OF MULTI-COMPONENT MATERIALS

2.1. Abrasive Wear Models

When various phases are combined, forming a multiphase material (Fig. 1), it is expected that the overall behaviour will be a function of the respective contribution of each phase [1]. Based on this approach, the wear resistance has been mathematically described as a linear function of the volume fraction of the phases present. In terms of total wear rate, i.e. inverse of wear resistance, the model is called the inverse rule of mixtures (IROM):

$$W^{-1} = \sum V_i W_i^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where W is the total volume wear rate, W^{-1} is the total wear resistance, W_i is the wear rate of the i phase and V_i is the volume fraction of the i phase.

It was demonstrated that this model predicts the wear behaviour of multiphase materials only when each phase shows a wear rate proportional to the applied load. That is the case for ductile metal systems. However, when hard phases and ceramic materials are involved, the IROM cannot be applied because the wear rate is non-linearly related to the load.

The other existing model is the linear rule of mixtures (LROM):

$$W = \sum V_i W_i \quad (2)$$

The relationship gives a balanced value of the wear rate without the predominant effect of any one phase. In general, it was pointed out that LROM is suitable to describe a combination of very similar phases while IROM better describes structures which consist of phases with very different properties.

Another important point is the particle-matrix interfacial bond strength. It can have the most significant effect in multiphase systems. The above models are based on no phase interaction. In fact, important micro-mechanisms like cracking, wear debris formation, decohesion and pulling out of the reinforcing phase can take place at interfaces [2].

In order to better understand the mechanisms involved in the total tribological system, the interacting effects among the geometrical factors must also be analysed. The total abrasive action on the multiphase system has to be considered as the macroscopic sum of each microscopic effect produced by an individual abrasive grain. Each of these wear micro-events generates a groove in the material. It is expected that the reinforcing role of a dispersed phase may change as the groove size is smaller or bigger than the microstructural size.

Fig. 1. Microstructural parameters in a two-phase isotropic material [1].

2.2. Abrasion of Particle Filled Polymer Composites

One of the main problems with particulate composite systems, as e.g. used for dental applications, are insufficient wear resistance. In the work by Prasad and Calvert [3] an inverse rule of mixtures was used to describe abrasive wear of such particulate composite materials in terms of the wear properties of the individual components. A full understanding of the abrasive wear of composites would, however, require a full understanding of abrasive wear of homogeneous materials. In the absence of this, the authors formulated a relationship similar to equ. (1) which was expected to give, at least, approximate values for composite wear rates in terms of the wear rates of the separate phases.

Wear rates for composites against quartz abrasive are shown in Fig. 2. In this case the wear rate drops markedly as silane-treated quartz particles are introduced into the resin. Wear rates of PMMA and quartz against the same quartz abrasive were 19.9 and $1.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$, respectively. Using these values and Equation 1 one can predict an even more marked decrease in wear rate. Non-silanated quartz fillers give little improvement in wear rate and glass beads (diameter of glass bead filler between 4 to $44 \mu\text{m}$) give an increased rate. The wear rate for glass sheet against abrasive was $25 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$ so that Equation 1 predicts a slight increase in wear rate with filler content but not as great as is observed.

Fig. 2. Wear rates of composites by $10 \mu\text{m}$ quartz abrasive. (∇) Silan-treated quartz filler, (\triangle) untreated quartz, (\diamond) untreated glass-bead filler [3].

2.3. Particulate Composites Under Sliding Wear Conditions

In order to show that the description of composites' wear rates by a simple, inverse rule of mixtures is not always applicable, a similar set of particulate reinforced, dental polymer composites was subjected to dry sliding wear conditions against a rotating smooth steel counterpart [4,5]. Figure 3 illustrates the course of the specific wear rates of these materials as a function of filler volume fraction. Both, the $2 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$ particle filled composites show, relative to the unfilled matrix, a little reduction in wear rate at low filler content (up to 10 volume %). Above this value, the composites' wear rates exceed that of the PMMA-matrix and run through a maximum, which is extremely higher and steeper for the $2 \mu\text{m}$ particulate composite than for the $10 \mu\text{m}$ system. After these maxima (which are at about $V_f = 20\%$ for the $10 \mu\text{m}$ and about 28% for the $2 \mu\text{m}$ composite) the values of both multiphase materials approach each other at a level comparable to that of the neat polymer (in the range above $V_f > 45\%$). Regarding the surface treatment of the fillers and the addition of an antioxidant, there was no systematic effect detectable in case of the $2 \mu\text{m}$ -particle system. Only in the maximum region of the $10 \mu\text{m}$ composite, the silane treated materials resulted in slightly better values of wear resistance.

The different trends in specific wear rate vs. filler volume fraction are here due to the action of various mechanisms which are mentioned in Figure 4, along with the actual curves resulting from them. The complexity doesn't allow to describe these curves by a simple rule of mixtures; the only

attempt which can be made to approach these trends mathematically is a semi-empirical relationship which includes (besides the rule of mixture components) special terms which account for the individual mechanisms dominating the composites' wear process in the various regions of V_f . A more simple development of such an equation has been performed by Friedrich and Voss [6] for sliding wear of short fiber composites.

Fig. 3. Specific wear rates of dental composites as a function of actual particle content. In addition the course of the particle distances $\lambda (V_f)$ in the different systems is illustrated.

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of the various trends due to the different wear mechanisms and the actual courses of curves resulting from them.

3. MODELS FOR SLIDING WEAR OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

3.1. Rule of Mixtures for Friction Coefficient

When a countersurface slides against an FRP surface, both normal load P and tangential force F are supported by fibers and matrix; therefore the friction coefficient μ can be given by

$$\frac{1}{\mu} = V_f \frac{1}{\mu_f} + V_m \frac{1}{\mu_m} \tag{3}$$

Using this equation Tzukizoe and Ohmae [7] were able to predict the friction coefficient μ of FRP when the friction coefficients of fiber μ_f and of matrix μ_m were given.

From the results in Fig. 5, it is clear that carbon fiber is the best reinforcement as far as the friction of FRP is concerned. The friction anisotropy depending on the fiber orientation relative to the sliding direction can not be recognized in this figure.

Fig. 5. Influence of volume fraction of fibers on the friction coefficient of polyester composites [7]. Different symbols refer to different fiber orientations.

3.2. Wear Mechanisms and Correlations with Other Mechanical Properties

Tzukizoe and Ohmae's results of corresponding wear tests have shown that the wear volume increases linearly with sliding distance; no running-in period of wear has been apparent in their case. Thus it was possible to characterize the wear in terms of a specific wear rate w_s , which has a unit of $\text{mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$ (Fig. 6). It is evident that HS-CFRP and HM-CFRP have a small specific wear rate of the order of $10^{-7} \text{mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$ and a low friction coefficient of 0.2. In contrast, GFRP and SFRP show a large specific wear rate of the order of $10^{-4} \text{mm}^3/(\text{Nm})$ and a high friction coefficient of 0.4. The lowest friction coefficient of 0.1 was obtained for CFRTP. Good tribological properties of carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics group (CFRTP, NT-CFRP and HM-CFRP) may be caused by the good mechanical properties of CFRP, for instance, high Young's modulus and high interlaminar shear strength, as well as by the good tribological properties of fibers, e.g., self-lubricating ability and high strength.

The authors proposed the following model of wear processes: The wear of FRP proceeds by a) wear thinning of the fiber-reinforcements, b) subsequent breakdown of the fibers, c) peeling-off of the fibers from the matrix, and a sequential occurrence of these processes governs the wear of FRP. The essential factors affecting these three processes may be as follows: a) in the wear thinning of the fiber : load P and sliding distance L ; b) in the breakdown of the fiber : strain $\mu P/E$ of FRP caused by friction force, load P and sliding distance L ; c) in the peeling-off of the fiber from the matrix : interlaminar shear strength I_s of FRP, strain $\mu P/E$ of FRP, load P and sliding distance L .

Fig. 6. Relation between specific wear rate and friction coefficient of various polymer matrix composites [7].

4. SYSTEMATIC DEVELOPMENT OF POLYMERIC HYBRID COMPOSITES FOR HIGH WEAR RESISTANCE

4.1. Ideas and Objectives

Hawthorne [8] reported on the sliding wear performance of glass- and carbon-fiber hybrid composites against steel. He found that a reasonable percentage of the more expensive carbon fibers could be replaced by the much cheaper glass fibers without losing much of the high wear-resistance measured for the composites reinforced with only carbon fibers. A similar result was found by Tzukizoe and Ohmae [7] who tried to describe the coefficient of friction and the wear behaviour of hybrid composites by a modified rule of mixtures.

All of these papers have in common, that some types of fibers under particular orientation can result in better improvements of the composites' wear resistance than others, which may be more favourable, however, when they are positioned under a different orientation relative to the wear direction. Bringing the favourable orientations and types of fibers together, may even lead to further improvements or to so called "synergistic" effects. As this had however been shown only for a few fiber/matrix combinations, a systematic study was established quite recently [9] which had the objectives of

- (a) to study the wear performance of quite a number of the major fiber/matrix combinations in a more systematic way as it was done before,
- (b) to develop from this information hybrid composites, which were expected to have, if possible, better wear resistance than that which could be expected from the simple rule of mixtures of the wear rates of the different monolithic constituents.

Efforts were concentrated only on the wear rate of these materials because, in most tribological situations, it is the wear life of a component rather than its coefficient of friction that determines its applicability.

4.2. Basic Materials and Testing Procedures

Different sets of unidirectionally oriented, continuous-fiber composites were used for the fundamental approach to the wear rates of monolithic composites. A description of the multiple-pass sliding wear studies, as performed with a standard pin-on-ring apparatus, is given in several previous papers, e.g. [10]. Briefly, the unidirectional (UD) composite samples are pressed against rotating steel rings (German Standard 100 Cr 6; initial roughness $R_a = 0.14\mu\text{m}$) with three principal fiber orientations: normal (N) to the sliding direction, in plane and parallel (P) to the sliding direction, and in plane but perpendicular (AP) to the sliding direction. All tests were carried out at room temperature in the laboratory environment and under pressure/velocity conditions of $p v = 1.7 \text{ MPa m s}^{-1}$.

4.3. Wear Rates of Monolithic Composites

Reinforcement of a polymeric matrix system by continuous fibers normally results in a reduction of the material wear rate. The relative improvement in wear resistance is, however, highly influenced by both the type of polymer matrix and the type of fiber used as reinforcement (Figure 7). The wear rates of the different matrix materials compared vary over a range of almost three orders of magnitude. The incorporation of carbon or aramid fibers brings the wear rates closer together (within one order of magnitude). In all cases, both types of fiber resulted in an improvement in wear behaviour, although this was much more pronounced for the rapidly wearing amorphous polyamide than for the more wear-resistant poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK). Glass-fiber composites exhibited 10- to 100-fold higher wear rates than the carbon or aramid fiber composites, and they wore even faster than the unreinforced matrix when the latter possessed a high wear resistance (PEEK, for instance).

In Table 1, all results obtained with the different matrices and composites, worn under different

Fig. 7. Matrix and fiber effects on sliding wear of unidirectional composites. The various symbols refer to different fiber materials and orientations in the different matrices. The exact values are given in the following figures.

Table 1. Wear-resistance ratios as normalized to the one of neat epoxy resin ($EP_1: \dot{w}_s^{-1} = 1.79 \cdot 10^4 \text{Nm/mm}^3$)

Matrix	Orientation	CF	GF	AF	Unreinforced
EP ₁	N	65.4	0.5	122.4	1
	P	99.8	2.1	44.1	
	AP	44.1	1.1	46.3	
PEEK	N	65.1	5.1	61.4	11.8
	P	158.1	5.5	46.1	
	AP	94.8	2.0	44.1	
amPA	N	117.7	—	145.5	0.07
	P	128.6	—	65.1	
	AP	57.0	—	102.4	
PA66	N	41.3	1.8	145.5	27.7
	P	122.9	16.3	60.8	
	AP	80.2	8.9	73.7	
EP ₂	N	102.4	—	104.3	1
	P	197.5	—	45.7	
	AP	90.7	—	75.8	

orientations, are summarized in terms of their wear resistance ratios (wear resistance of the materials normalized to that of the unfilled epoxy). The higher this quantity is above unity, the better is the composite in this particular direction in comparison to the isotropic standard (unreinforced epoxy). All ratios above an arbitrarily chosen value of 90 (i.e. 90 times higher sliding wear resistance than epoxy) are printed in large characters for better comparison. The following conclusions can be drawn from Table 1:

- carbon-fibers in parallel orientation and/or aramid fibers in normal orientation have resulted in the best wear resistance values of the composites (regardless of the type of matrix);
- carbon fibers in the AP or N directions may also sometimes lead to good results;
- glass fibers are ineffective in relation to carbon or aramid fibers; if, however, the glass fibers should be incorporated in the composite for other reasons, their arrangement should be in the P orientation, or, less ideally, in the AP direction, but not in the N orientation;
- among the unreinforced matrices, tougher semi-crystalline thermoplastics (e.g. PEEK and polyamide 6.6) result in higher wear resistances than amorphous PA or a cross-linked, more brittle epoxy resin.

4.4. Wear Studies on Hybrid Composites

From the conclusions drawn above, a model composite can be designed that combines all the favorable fiber types and orientations in one structure. A composite with an overall good wear resistance could be made, for example, by three-dimensional hybridization, with interwoven carbon fibers in plane (X-Y-plane) and aramid fibers in the Z-direction. The matrix should be a tough,

highly wear-resistant thermoplastic polymer (Fig. 8).

Of course, such a hypothetical 3-D hybrid structure cannot very easily be verified. But it is at least possible to approach such a structure along two lines. One is to study 2-D woven-fabric composites, e.g. carbon-fiber woven-fabric reinforced PEEK. In fact, this has been done in previous work [11]; it was shown that the woven structure resulted in a better wear-resistance and a lower coefficient of friction than the two basic orientations of the unidirectional material.

Another approach to the hybrid model composite is to combine layers of different fiber types and orientations within one laminate. This can result in either a sandwich or a layer structure. The majority of the materials made here contained carbon and aramid fibers in a cross-ply sandwich form.

Fig. 8. Design concept for a hybrid composite with good wear resistance.

As a positive example, Figure 9 represents the specific wear rates of hybrid composites consisting of normally oriented aramid fiber and parallel carbon fiber in a PA matrix. The arrangement of the aramid fiber in the sandwich core resulted in a positive hybrid effect, i.e. the wear rates for the hybrid were lower than that expected from a simple rule of mixtures (IROM), as based on the wear rates of the two components when being tested separately. It is shown further that a layer hybrid yields better improvements in the wear resistance than a simple sandwich structure.

Fig. 9. Specific wear rates of aramid-fiber/carbon-fiber/PA 6.6 hybrids.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

It can be stated from the results of this review paper that many different polymer composites can be used for friction and wear applications. They can be tailored with regards to their load carrying capacity, their temperature and creep resistance, their coefficient of friction, and their resistance to abrasion and wear under sliding against steel counterparts. But in spite of (a) the wide variety of existing material systems for these applications, and (b) the flexibility in tailoring polymer composites for a particular property profile, there are still further studies necessary in order to obtain a full understanding of their tribological performance. A basic help to reach this objective can be achieved from some further references not yet mentioned in the previous context [11-17]. These include informations about the role of fatigue crack propagation in the wear of polymeric tribosystems, about how to select polymer composites for friction and wear applications, and about the construction of wear mechanism maps helpful to understand the wear rate transitions and their relationship to wear mechanisms.

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